

Research Article

A Critical Appraisal of the Causes and Consequences of Low Productivity Among
Civil Servants in Ondo State

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Abstract

The civil service in Nigeria has been overwhelmed with ever-increasing responsibilities, and there should be better restructuring to meet the numerous expectations of the government and the citizenry. Thus, this study aims to critically appraise the causes and consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State and proper remedies to the overarching challenges. The study elicited data from both primary and secondary sources. A sample size of 800 respondents was purposively selected through systematic sampling techniques from eight (8) ministries and four (4) agencies in Ondo State. The study relies on Taylor's theory and Maslow's theory of the hierarchy of needs as a theoretical foundation. The findings revealed that the Ondo State civil service has a long history of poor remuneration, inadequate and incompetent workers, leadership problems, inadequate training, poor compensation and motivation, indiscipline, nepotism, poor funding of ministries and agencies, contributing significantly to the low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State. The study also revealed that low productivity can lead to economic losses, retrenchment of workers, lack of innovation and creativity, delays of job completion, among others. The study concluded that the present low productivity among the undermotivated staff must be quickly addressed to prevent further economic ruin. Therefore, the study recommended motivation of workers through fair salaries, recruitment of qualified job seekers, training and retraining of workers, participation in decision-making leadership, de-politicisation of civil service, proper funding of government establishments, enforcement of discipline and other panaceas to increase workforce productivity in Ondo State.

Keywords: Civil servants, government, leadership, population, productivity.

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Introduction

Background of the Study

The civil service has always been the tool available to the Nigerian government for the implementation of developmental goals and objectives. It is seen as a pivot for the growth of the Nigerian economy. Amoako-Gyampah and Acquah (2003) (2003) observed that it is responsible for the creation of an appropriate and conducive environment in which the economy can perform optimally, and it is this catalytic role of the civil service that propelled governments all over the world to search continuously for better ways to deliver their services. Civil Service is the instrument that the government uses to regulate and manage all aspects of society. Thus, the condition of a society is largely determined by the public service. Besides, it is from this government bureaucracy that all the other institutions obtain various types of approval, license and permits which are critical to their existence and operation. Also, government allocations of resources pass through the bureaucracy to all other areas of society directly and indirectly. Therefore, Philips (1990) observed that all other institutions perform have to deal with the civil service at one point or another in their existence and operations.

In many developing countries like Nigeria, Nunberg (1994) opined that the civil service is frequently too expensive and insufficiently productive, and civil servants, especially those in management positions, get few incentives and are poorly motivated. Many low-income countries have taken important steps in first-generation reforms, that is, based on restructuring and downsizing the civil service. Yet, beyond a certain point, Lienert (1998) argues that cutting costs by squeezing real wages becomes counterproductive as skilled staff members leave the civil service; those who remain become demoralised and absenteeism, moonlighting and corruption increase. In the view of Schiavo-campo (1998), overemphasis on cost-containment as an end in itself has, by the way, given civil service a bad name, maximising resistance to reforms and ultimately nullifying the very savings from cost-containment itself. To address these problems, countries have been attempting to lead second-generation reforms aimed at revamping pay and promotion policies. Lienert (1998) believed that the multiple objectives of first-generation reforms can give

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rise to conflicts, and little progress has been made in second-generation reforms.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian civil service, like the Ondo State civil service, is constrained by physical, organisational and institutional structures that seriously limit the productivity of workers. Observations show that civil servants in Nigeria are generally lazy and often display a lackadaisical attitude to official assignments.

- Documentation
- Drafting of bills
- Making of bye-laws
- Stability and
- Budget preparation.

It is the duty of a civil servant to be involved in the implementation of policies faithfully and loyally to make available good roads, water supply, electricity, the establishment of industries, schools, and hospitals, among others (Marvellous and Monday, 2016; Ene, 2023).

According to Nebo and Nnamani (2015a) and Nebo and Namani (2015b), the Nigerian civil service has been compromised by politicization, insubordination, corruption, sabotage, mediocrity, low morale, nepotism and bribery, leading to the inability of the organisation to attain predetermined goals or increased productive capacity.

Unfortunately, the past attempts of the governments through reforms and recommendations geared towards converting inputs into gainful outputs in order to achieve the set goals have not yielded the desired result. The civil service still remains backward, inefficient and ineffective in terms of service delivery.

Against this backdrop, this study is interested in providing remedies to the challenges of low productivity among Ondo State civil servants. The general objective of this study is to critically appraise low productivity among Ondo State civil servants. Specifically, this study is set to:

- (1) To assess the level of productivity among civil servants in Ondo State.
- (2) To determine the level of effectiveness of government reforms to enhance productivity among civil servants.
- (3) To appraise the militating factors against civil servants' productivity in Ondo State.

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- (4) To examine the consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions for this study

- (1) What is the level of productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?
- (2) What is the level of effectiveness of government reforms to enhance productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?
- (3) What are the militating factors against civil servants' productivity in Ondo State?
- (4) What are the consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?

Significance of the Study

The study will assist the government and policymakers in holistically addressing the problems of low productivity among the servants in Ondo State. The civil servants will also benefit from the recommendations of this study if implemented by the government. The study will definitely serve as a source of information to guide future researchers in the particular field or related fields. The uncooperative attitude of those given the questionnaire to fill constituted a major obstacle. Many hid under the civil service oath of secrecy, which prohibits civil servants from divulging sensitive information without prior authorisation from their superiors. Scope and delimitation in terms of scope, this study was to specifically determine the causes and consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was used. This method entails the study of more than one variable of a population of interest at some time. The descriptive approach involves the normal gathering, analysis and interpretation of data so as to explain the underlying factors that surround the problems that triggered the research. The study involves the collection of data through questionnaires and observations.

Study Population

The study population comprises 200 civil servants from grades 7 - 17 with at least 10 years in the employment of the Ondo State government.

Samples and Sampling Techniques

The 200 samples were purposively selected using a systematic sampling technique from the following government establishment.

- Ondo State Ministry of Information and Orientation
- Ondo State Civil Service Commission
- Ondo State Ministry of Youth and Sport Development and
- Ondo State Ministry of Health

All these are situated in Akure, the capital of Ondo State. 55 respondents were selected from the Ondo State Ministry of Youth and Sports Development. 35 respondents from the Ondo State Ministry of Information, 46 respondents from the Ondo State Civil Service Commission and 64 respondents from the ODSMH.

Instruments for data collection

The instruments used for the study were obtained from primary sources (questionnaires, interviews, observations) and secondary sources (published journals, magazines, newspapers, and internet materials that are related to the study). The major instrument used for data collection was the self-designed questionnaire because it provided relevant information with tolerable accuracy and completeness.

Administration of the instruments

The researcher and his three assistants administered the well-structured questionnaire containing formalised set of questions to the respondents in the government establishments visited. Where needed, the items of the questionnaire were explained and interpreted to the respondents in order to elicit accurate responses from them. The answers provided to both closed and open-ended questions were recorded. The researcher's personal contact and visit to the respondents helped in a better understanding of the instrument and also eased the retrieval of the instruments.

The responses were coded to maintain confidentiality.

Validity of Instruments

The truth and accuracy of the research define the validity (Ord et al., 2021). Validity tests were conducted for content, criterion and construct to test how well the instrument is representative, captures relationships between the variables and measures the concepts. The questionnaire was validated by the researcher's supervisor and other experts in order to ascertain the face and content validity.

Content validity ratio was used to calculate the content validity index, using the formula

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below.

$$CV1 = \frac{\text{Total number of items rated by all respondents}}{\text{Total number of items in the instrument}}$$

$$CV1 = \frac{61}{82}$$

$$CV1 = 0.74$$

A content validity index of 0.7 and above, according to Amin (2005), qualified the instrument for the study.

Reliability of instruments

Reliability refers to the accuracy of data in relation to stability, repeatability, and precision (Idowu, 2005). An instrument is reliable when it is persistent in measuring correctly what it is supposed to measure, with the result remaining the same when administered in a similar situation at different times or by different scholars.

Method of data collection

The method of data collection for this study is purposive sampling, which involved identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that were knowledgeable about or experienced with the phenomenon of interest (Cresswell and Plano-Clark, 2011). This sampling was used to select 800 civil servants across 5 Ondo State government establishments. The quantitative data collection method was applied from the questionnaires that were filled by these civil servants at different grade levels who had spent at least 10 years in the service of the Ondo State government. The field work was carried out between July and November 2024.

Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaire collected from the respondents was presented and analysed. The analysed data were presented using frequency, tables and simple percentages.

Results and Discussion

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

This section describes the socio-demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile

Variable Group	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
21-30	35	17.5
31-40	66	33
41-50	78	39
51-60	21	10.5
Total	200	100
Marital Status		
Single	17	8.5
Married	119	59.5
Divorced	43	21.5
Widowed	7	13.5
Total	200	100
Education Status		
University Graduates	91	45
Polytechnic graduates	39	19.5
School of Nursing graduates	43	21.5
Secondary school certificate holders	27	13.5
Total	200	100
Years of experience		
10-14	18	9
15-19	62	31
20-24	81	40.5
25-29	39	19.5
Total	200	100

Table 1 presents the analysis of ages of respondents – out of 200 respondents, 35 respondents representing 17.5% are between the age bracket of 21-30 years; 66(33%) are between the age bracket of 31-40 years; 78(39%) fell within 51-60years. It can then be

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inferred from the results that the majority of the respondents are between 31 and 40 years old. Similarly, the table presented the analysis of the education status of the 200 respondents, revealing that 91 (45.5%) respondents are university graduates, 39(19.5%) are polytechnic graduates, 43(21.5%) graduated from a school of Nursing, while 27 (13.5%) are secondary school certificate holders. The results showed that the majority of the respondents are educated. In the same vein, the table presented the years of experience of the respondents with the Ondo State government. 18(9%) respondents have spent between 10-14years in service; 62(3%) have spent between 15 – 19 years; 81(40.5%) have spent between 20-24years; 39(19.5%) have spent between 25-29years. The result showed that the majority of the respondents have spent between 20 and 24 years in the service of the Ondo State government.

Table 2: Grade level of respondents

Grade level of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
7-10	108	54
12-17	92	46
Total	200	100

Source: field survey 2023

Table 2 presented the analysis of the grade levels of the respondents. The table revealed that civil servants on grade 7-10 are 108 (54%) while 92 (45%) respondents are on grade levels 12-16. In civil service, grade 11 does not exist. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are middle-level civil servants.

Research question 1: What is the level of productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?

Table 3: Respondents' opinion on the level of productivity among civil servants

Level of productivity	Frequency	Percentage
Low	126	63
Average	48	24
High	26	13
Total	200	100

Source: Field study 2023

Table 3 presents the analysis of respondents' responses on the level of productivity. 126(63%) respondents opined that there is a low level of workers' productivity in Ondo State civil service; 48(24%) opined that the productivity level is average, and 26(13%) respondents opined that the level of productivity is high. The result shows that the

majority of the respondents agreed that there is a low level of productivity in the Ondo State civil service.

Research Question 2: What are the factors militating against workers' productivity in Ondo State?

Table 4: Respondents opinion on the factors militating against workers productivity

Militating factors	Frequency	Percentage
Inadequate skills	49	24.5
Poor salaries	39	19.5
Lack of training	16	8
Leadership problem	34	17
Indiscipline	19	2.5
Nepotism	13	6.5
Poor funding of the MDAs	30	15
Total	200	100

Source: field study 2023

Table 4 presents the analysis of respondents' opinions on factors that militate against workers' productivity in the Ondo State civil service. The table revealed that 49(24.5%) respondents agreed that inadequate skills is responsible for the low productivity among civil servants in other state; 39(19.5%) agreed that it is the poor salaries; 16(8%) agreed that it is lack of trainings; 34(17%) agreed it is leadership problem; 30(15%) agreed it is poor funding of the ministries, department and agencies. The results show that the majority of the respondents agreed that the inadequate skills of the civil servants are responsible for the low productivity.

Research question 3: What is the level of effectiveness of government reforms to enhance productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?

Table 4 presents the results of the respondents on the level of effectiveness of government reforms on civil servants' productivity. The table revealed that 17(8.5%) respondents disagreed. The result shows that the majority of respondents agreed that government reforms are not effective in enhancing productivity among civil servants in Ondo State.

Research question 4: What are the consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State?

Table 5: Respondents’ opinion on the consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State.

Consequences of low production	Frequency	Percentage
Economic losses	3	46.5
Retrenchment	22	11
Lack of creativity and innovation	8	47
Delay of jobs completion	36	18
Poor standard of living	41	20.5
Total	200	100

Source: Field study 2024

Table 5 presents the respondents' opinions on the consequences of low productivity among civil servants in Ondo State. The table revealed that 93(46.5%) respondents agreed that low productivity causes economic loss 22(11%) opined that retrenchment of workers can arise as a result of low productivity; 8(4%) agreed on lack of creativity and innovation; 36(18%) agreed on delay of job completion while 41(20.5%) respondents agreed on poor standard of living among workers.

The result shows that the majority of respondents agreed that low productivity results to economic losses.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

The study concluded that the Nigerian civil service, like the Ondo State civil service, is dominated by unskilled workers who are undermotivated and poorly remunerated. The workers display a lack of commitment, indiscipline, absenteeism, and other corrupt practices like falsification of ages and certificates, among other untoward attitudes, with their concomitant consequences on the level of productivity. The study also concluded that the level of the present workers' productivity is low and can result in economic ruin.

Recommendations

Having juxtaposed the findings of the previous studies with these present findings, the study hereby recommends the following measures that will improve the productivity of workers in the service of the Ondo State government.

1. There should be improved welfare packages for the civil servants, as the present salaries cannot sustain the level of productivity expected from the workforce. Salaries and wages of civil servants should be reviewed in the face of the present realities.

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2. The working environments should be improved upon
3. Enforcement of rewards and discipline among workers
4. Training and re-training of workers
5. De-politicization of civil services
6. Recruitment of workers and appointment of political heads should be based on merit
7. Participatory leadership must be encouraged to promote the collective decision-making process
8. Proper funding of the government establishments will ensure the efficiency of workers.

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APPENDIX TWO - SECTION A

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Kindly respond by ticking the response as it occurs to you using the format below. You may as well supply other information where necessary.

1. Name
2. Gender: Male () Female ()
3. Agee: (a) 21-30 years (b) 31-40years (c) 41-50years
4. Academic qualifications
Secondary school certificate () Polytechnic graduate ()
School of nursing () university graduates ()
5. Marital Status (a) single (b) married (c) divorced (d) widowed
6. Years of service (a) 10-14 years (b)15-19years (c) 20-24years (d) 25-29years
7. Grade level (a) 7-10 (b) 12-17

B - PSYCHOGRAPHIC DATA

1. What is the level of productivity among Ondo State civil servants?
(a) low (b) average (c) high
2. Does possession of inadequate skills militate against Ondo State civil servants' productivity?
Yes () No ()
3. Does poor remuneration militate against Ondo State civil servants' productivity?
Yes () No ()
4. Does leadership problem militate against Ondo State civil servants productivity?
Yes () No ()
5. Does indiscipline militate against Ondo State civil servants productivity?
6. Does Nepotism against Ondo State civil servants productivity?
Yes () No ()
7. Does poor funding of ministries departments and agencies (MDAs) against Ondo State civil servants productivity?
Yes () No ()
8. What is the level of effectiveness of government reforms on Ondo State civil servants' productivity?
(a) very effective (b) moderately effective (c) not effective
9. Is economy losses a consequence of low productivity among Ondo State civil

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- servants?
Yes () No ()
10. Is retrenchment a consequence of low productivity among Ondo State civil servants?
Yes () No ()
11. Is lack of creativity and innovation a consequence of how productivity among Ondo State civil servant?
Yes () No ()
12. Is delay of jobs completion a consequence of low productivity among Ondo State civil service?
Yes () No ()
13. Is poor standard of living a consequence of low productivity among Ondo State civil servants?
Yes () No ()